

20NRM04 MetrIAQ

D6: Report on the preparation and measurement uncertainty of ERMs, gPRM and gCRMs

Authors: Christoph Grimmer¹, Matthias Richter¹, Iris de Krom², Adriaan van der Veen², Frederick Maes³, Maricarmen Lecuna⁴, Thomas Neuhaus⁵, Anna Musyanovych⁶

Lead partner: **BAM**¹

Other partners: VSL², VITO³, POLITO⁴, Eurofins⁵, FhG⁶

Due date of the deliverable: 31 May 2024

Actual submission date of the deliverable: 16 July 2024

Bundesanstalt für Materialforschung
und -prüfung (BAM)
Unter den Eichen 87
12205 Berlin
GERMANY

VSL,
Chemistry group
Thijsseweg 11
2629 JA Delft
the Netherlands

VITO
Unit HEALTH
Boeretang 200
2400 Mol
Belgium

**POLITECNICO
DI TORINO**

Politecnico di Torino
Corso Duca degli Abruzzi, 24
10129 Torino
ITALY

Eurofins Product Testing Denmark A/S
Smedskovvej 38
8464 Galten
DENMARK

Fraunhofer Institute for
Microengineering and Microsystems
IMM
Carl-Zeiss-Str. 18-20
55129 Mainz
GERMANY

Summary

This is a report about the preparation and measurement uncertainty of reference materials developed in the European Metrology Programme for Innovation and Research (EMPIR) project *Metrology for the determination of emissions of dangerous substances from building materials into indoor air* (20NRM04 MetrIAQ). The overall aim of the MetrIAQ project is to develop traceable measurement of emissions of volatile organic compounds (VOC) from such materials by providing well-defined emission reference materials (ERM) and certified reference gas standards (gCRM), in accordance with the quality control requirements of the emission test chamber procedure described in EN 16516. During the project these reference materials were validated, and a full uncertainty budget was obtained based on the combined uncertainty sources of the reference materials, e.g., preparation, reproducibility, stability and accuracy.

The preparation uncertainty is not accessible for the herein used ERMs. But the measurement uncertainty of the analysis method, of parameters of the emission test chamber and the ERM was determined with data from the development, internal validation and interlaboratory comparison part 2. The uncertainty of the overall procedure depends highly on the tested ERM and was determined to be in the domain of about 20–50 %.

Based on the validation and stability study of the gPRM and gCRM, a relative expanded uncertainty of 5 % was obtained for gPRMs prepared dynamically. Static gPRMs, in cylinders, have relative expanded uncertainties between 8–16 %.

Table of Contents

1	Introduction	6
2	Methods	7
2.1	Methods concerning the ERMs.....	7
2.1.1	Generation of ERMs	7
2.1.2	Emission test chamber procedure.....	7
2.1.3	Analysis (TD-GC-MS/-FID)	7
2.2	Methods concerning the gPRM and gCRM	7
2.2.1	Stability study gPRMs.....	8
2.2.2	Long-term stability gCRMs	9
3	Measurement uncertainty of emission reference materials.....	10
3.1	Uncertainty of the analysis method.....	10
3.2	Uncertainty of the emission test chamber procedure.....	11
3.3	Uncertainty of sampling	12
3.4	Uncertainty of emission reference materials	12
4	Uncertainty of gPRM and gCRM.....	15
4.1	Uncertainty of the dynamic gPRM	15
4.2	Uncertainty static gPRM	16
4.3	Uncertainty gCRMs in sorbent tubes.....	17
5	Conclusion	18
Annex 1	Validation data of the analysis method used for the emission testing of ERMs.....	19
A1.1	Repeatability data.....	19
A1.2	Reproducibility data	19
Annex 2	Exemplary chamber characterisation of a chamber used for the emission testing of ERMs	20
A2.1	Homogeneity and stability of temperature and relative humidity.....	20
A2.2	Pressure.....	20
A2.3	Air exchange rate	21
A2.4	Air flow velocity over sample	22
Annex 3	Results stability study static gPRMs	24
References	32

1 Introduction

Considering that European citizens spend more than 80 % of their time indoors, it is vital to have a healthy indoor environment. To achieve this, the release of harmful substances from building materials, such as paints, flooring, and from other products into the indoor air must be minimised. Reliable, accurate and traceable measurements of these emissions are paramount to reach high level consumer protection.

The overall aim of the MetrIAQ project (*Metrology for the determination of emissions of dangerous substances from building materials into indoor air*) is to develop traceable measurement of emissions of volatile organic compounds (VOC) from such materials by providing well-defined emission reference materials (ERM) and certified reference gas standards (gCRM), in accordance with the emission test chamber procedure described in EN 16516 [1].

Reference materials are materials of sufficient homogeneity with one or several well-defined properties [2, 3]. In case of emission reference materials, this property is the emission behaviour (emission rate at a specific time) and “well-defined” includes the reference value and its uncertainty. Two different approaches were used for the generation of ERMs: the impregnation of porous materials with selected VOCs, and the encapsulation of VOCs by polymerisation (μ -capsules). Four VOCs (*n*-hexane, toluene, 2-ethyl-1-hexanol and D-limonene) were used for the generation of ERMs.

Gaseous Primary Reference Materials (gPRMs) and gaseous Certified Reference Materials (gCRMs) were developed containing trace levels of VOCs in nitrogen or air. The selected VOCs (*n*-hexane, methyl isobutyl ketone, toluene, butyl acetate, cyclohexanone, *o*-xylene, phenol, 1,3,5-trimethylbenzene) are chosen based on the check standard described by EN 16516. Static gPRMs have been prepared in high pressure cylinders according to ISO 6142-1 [4] and gPRMs and gCRMs were prepared dynamically according to ISO 6145-4 [5]. The gPRMs and gCRMs can be sampled into sorbent tubes, according to ISO 16017-1 [6], to obtain gCRMs for quality assurance and quality control (QA/QC).

In this report, the preparation and measurement uncertainty of gaseous primary and gaseous certified reference materials is given. For the herein described emission reference materials, which cannot be easily traced back to primary units, only the measurement uncertainty can be determined. Information was taken from the development, the interlaboratory comparisons (part 1 and 2) and validation experiments.

2 Methods

2.1 Methods concerning the ERMs

2.1.1 Generation of ERMs

The reservoir materials for the ERMs have been prepared in two ways, on the one hand by impregnation of porous materials and on the other hand by encapsulation of the target compound. A brief description is given below:

The impregnation of porous materials is conducted with help of an autoclave and CO₂. A portion of porous material and VOC are placed into the autoclave, CO₂ is introduced, and the pressure and temperature is increased to 32 °C and 74 bar. After a few minutes, the pressure and temperature are reduced, and the impregnated material can be removed from the autoclave.

The encapsulation of VOC droplets is conducted at the droplets' interface in aqueous solution. Several different reagents and a portion of VOC are mixed, and then pressed through a Shirasu porous glass membrane. The resulting droplets are stabilised by a surfactant. More reagents are added and a polymeric wall forms at the droplets' interface.

A detailed description of the preparation processes is published elsewhere [7].

2.1.2 Emission test chamber procedure

The ERMs are placed into emission test chambers. The chambers are run with the typical parameters (temperature of 23 °C, relative humidity of 50 % and an air exchange rate of 0.5 h⁻¹ among others) according to EN 16516. Most experiments, concerning the determination of measurement uncertainty, were run in 270 L chambers at BAM, 119 L chambers at Eurofins or differently sized chambers (20–500 L) of the participants of the ILC part 2. The chamber air is regularly sampled with Tenax[®] TA tubes.

2.1.3 Analysis (TD-GC-MS/-FID)

The Tenax[®] TA tubes were measured with help of TD-GC-MS or TD-GC-FID. The devices are calibrated and checked on a regular basis. A detailed description of the analysis methods is given elsewhere [8].

2.2 Methods concerning the gPRM and gCRM

The preparation and validation of the gPRMs and gCRMs can be found in D3: Report on the preparation and analysis of gPRMs and gCRMs of indoor air pollutants state

in the EU-LCI list with relative uncertainties below 5 % ($k = 2$) and a shelf life of at least 1 year [9]. After finalising report D3 the stability of the gPRMs and gCRMs was further investigated to determine the contribution of the stability in the uncertainty calculation.

2.2.1 Stability study gPRMs

In report D3 the stability study of 4 static gas mixtures in high pressure cylinders was reported over a period of 12 months. This study was further expanded to a period of 22 months for 8 static gas mixtures in 3 different cylinder treatment types (**Table 1**).

Table 1. Overview stability study of gPRMs.

gPRM number	Amount fraction per VOC	Cylinder treatment	First 12 months reported in D3
VSL114005	$\sim 1 \mu\text{mol mol}^{-1}$	Experis NO	No
VSL114043	$\sim 1 \mu\text{mol mol}^{-1}$	Experis NO	No
VSL114044	$\sim 50 \text{ nmol mol}^{-1}$	Experis NO	Yes
VSL114045	$\sim 50 \text{ nmol mol}^{-1}$	Experis NO	Yes
VSL187546	$\sim 50 \text{ nmol mol}^{-1}$	Spectra Seal	Yes
VSL187555	$\sim 50 \text{ nmol mol}^{-1}$	Spectra Seal	Yes
VSL361130	$\sim 50 \text{ nmol mol}^{-1}$	Experis VOC	No
VSL270608	$\sim 50 \text{ nmol mol}^{-1}$	Experis VOC	No

To determine the stability of the VOCs in the static gPRMs after preparation, the gPRMs were sampled into sorbent tubes at $t = 2$ weeks, 2 months, 3 months, 7 months, 9 months, 13 months, 19 months and 22 months. After sampling, the tubes were analysed using TD-GC-FID. The GC was calibrated with tubes sampled from the dynamic gPRM. The dynamic gPRM was prepared at the same time as the sorbent tubes were sampled from the static gPRMs. Two methods have been used to determine if the VOCs are stable in the static gPRMs, 1) initial loss; looking at the deviation between the measured amount fraction and the gravimetric amount fraction of the VOCs in the static gPRMs. The VOCs are not stable in the static gPRM if the deviation of one or more stability measurements is larger than the expanded uncertainty and 2) long term instability; if the slope of the interpolation function (calculated using ordinary least squares regression), based on stability measurements, was smaller than two times its associated standard uncertainty the stability measurements show a horizontal trend and no instability (**Table 2** and **Annex 3**). The results for phenol were not processed, as it was evident from visual inspection of the data that the mixtures were unstable with respect to the amount fraction of this component.

Table 2. Results stability study for the three different cylinder treatments tested.

VOC	Experis NO		Spectra Seal		Experis VOC	
	Initial loss	Long Term Instability	Initial loss	Long Term Instability	Initial loss	Long Term Instability
n-Hexane	Yes	No	No	Yes	Yes	No
MIBK	Yes	No	Yes	No	No	No
Toluene	Yes	No	Yes	No	No	No
Butyl acetate	Yes	No	Yes	Yes	Yes	No
Cyclohexanone	Yes	No	Yes	Yes	Yes	No
o-Xylene	Yes	Yes	Yes	No	No	No
1,3,5-TMB	Yes	No	Yes	No	Yes	No

All 3 cylinder treatments show initial loss of several VOCs. Treatment 2 shows long term instability for several components, treatment 1 only for *o*-xylene and treatment 3 shows no long-term instability for the VOCs. Based on the results there is initial loss for all treatment types. This could be caused during preparation of the gas mixture or due to absorption to the cylinder wall. Thereafter the gas mixtures are stable for all VOCs when using cylinder type 3. To take the initial loss into account it was added as an uncertainty source for the uncertainty calculation.

2.2.2 Long-term stability gCRMs

The short-term stability of the gCRMs on sorbent tubes was reported in deliverable D3. The study was further expanded with a long-term stability study over a period of 6 months. The gCRMs in sorbent tubes were prepared by pumped sampling of known volumes of a dynamic gas mixture with the VOCs in air. The sampled tubes were analysed immediately after sampling, after 3 months and after 6 months (**Figure 1**). Meanwhile the tubes were stored at room temperature. The VOCs are stable on the sorbent tubes for a period of 6 months when stored at room temperature.

Figure 1. Results long term stability study gCRMs.

3 Measurement uncertainty of emission reference materials

Since the herein used ERMs are no primary reference materials, it is not possible to easily determine the measurement uncertainty, or parts of it, such as the repeatability or reproducibility, reference values etc., based on the generation procedure. The measurement uncertainty needs to be determined by measuring the ERMs in an emission test chamber. Thus, the uncertainty will consist of the uncertainty of the analysis, sampling, operational parameters of the emission test chamber and the ERM. Some parts of it can be isolated with relative ease (such as the analysis and sampling). Other parts, such as the uncertainty of the emission test chamber and the ERM, cannot be easily isolated from each other. In addition, a lot of chambers and/or a long period of time are needed to conduct enough measurements for statistical significance.

3.1 Uncertainty of the analysis method

The uncertainty of the TD-GC-FID method was determined with help of a quality control standard (QC). We used Tenax[®] TA tubes, that were spiked with 1 µL of an in-house calibration solution (100 ng/µL for each VOC). Two QC tubes were measured per week over a course of 4 weeks. The TD-GC-FID was calibrated at the beginning and end of every month with the same calibration standard, and with a freshly generated calibration standard at the beginning of the following

month. Cross-checking the results of the different calibration measurements (i.e., beginning vs. end of the month, old vs. new solution) boosts the trust in the device and the in-house generated calibration solutions. It was found that *n*-hexane evaporates from the calibration solution (stored at $-20\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$), which can lead to significant deviation within a few weeks. However, *n*-hexane, spiked into Tenax TA tubes and stored at $-20\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$, remained stable for at least 8 weeks. Thus, calibration and QC tubes were stored this way.

The repeatability was determined as the relative standard deviation (%) of 5 consecutive QC tube measurements. The reproducibility was determined as the relative standard deviation of 8 QC tube measurement over the course of 4 weeks. The relative expanded measurement uncertainty can be assigned based on s_R ($k = 2$).

Table 3. Repeatability (s_r), reproducibility (s_R) and expanded uncertainty (U , $k = 2$) of the TD-GC-FID method at BAM.

VOC	s_r (%)	s_R (%)	U (%)
<i>n</i> -hexane	4.5	4.8	9.6
toluene	1.9	2.7	5.5
2-ethyl-1-hexanol	0.9	5.8	11.5
D-limonene	1.7	1.6	3.1

3.2 Uncertainty of the emission test chamber procedure

Data from the characterisation of the 1 m^3 chamber is given below. Different experiments, measurements and sensors were used to determine the mean value, instability and sometimes inhomogeneity of important chamber parameters (**Table 4**). The measurement uncertainty (U) was calculated with a coverage factor of $k = 2$.

The temperature was measured with an array of sensors, that were distributed in the chamber (see **Annex 2**). This way, it is possible to determine the instability ($0.004\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$) and the inhomogeneity ($0.11\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$) of the temperature within the chamber. The values indicate a very small temperature fluctuation and a good homogeneity (i.e., no cold spots for condensation). The relative humidity (rel. h.) was measured with the same array of sensors. The mean value was 51.4% , the instability was 0.7% and the inhomogeneity was 0.36% .

The inlet air flow was determined with a gas meter and corrected for standard conditions ($23\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ and 1 atm). The air exchange rate was determined with help of the tracer gas method using nitrogen oxide (N_2O) (**Annex 2**). The chamber volume in turn was calculated by dividing the inlet air flow with the air exchange rate.

In a previous study, the pressure was measured for a week with help of a sensor and compared to the data of a weather station close to BAM. It was found that both are well correlated and differ by only 1 hPa . So, the data from the weather station was corrected by 1 hPa and used to calculate the mean value (1024.4 hPa)

and fluctuation (19.4 hPa) of the pressure within the chamber for an exemplary week. The pressure is, of course, highly dependent on the weather.

The air flow over the sample was measured for different points in the chamber (see **Annex 2**). A position for the sample was chosen, where the mean value is 0.2 m/s and the fluctuation 0.1 m/s.

Table 4. Mean valued, standard deviations and measurement uncertainty (U , $k = 2$) of important chamber parameters, when the 1 m³ chamber is set to standard conditions.

Parameter	Mean value	Standard deviation	U (k = 2)	Unit
Temperature	23.09	0.004 ^a	0.5 ^c	°C
Relative humidity	51.4	0.7 ^b	1.4 ^c	%
Air inlet flow	518.9	4.1	8.2	L/h
Air exchange rate	0.509	0.004	0.008	h ⁻¹
Chamber volume	1019.5 ^d	16.1 ^d	32.2 ^d	L
Pressure	1024.4 ^e	19.4 ^e	38.8 ^e	hPa
Air flow over sample	0.2	0.1	0.2	m/s

^a Temperature inhomogeneity = 0.11 °C, ^b Relative humidity inhomogeneity = 0.36 %, ^c Extended uncertainty type b, ^d Determined by $V = (\text{air inlet flow}/\text{air exchange rate})$, ^e Example for a testing duration of one week – depends highly on the weather.

3.3 Uncertainty of sampling

The sampling was conducted with help of a sampling pump, a mass flow meter and sorption tubes. The mass flow meter measures the sampling volume quite accurate with an uncertainty of less than 5 %. Thus, the expanded uncertainty of sampling is 10 %.

3.4 Uncertainty of emission reference materials

For the ERMs, we differentiate between in-batch repeatability (consecutive measurements of an ERM from the same batch by one laboratory), batch-to-batch repeatability (measurements of different batches of the same ERM by one laboratory), in-batch reproducibility (measurements of an ERM from the same batch by different laboratories) and batch-to-batch reproducibility (measurements of different batches of the same ERM by different laboratories). Further differentiation can be done between short-term and long-term repeatability. Here, we only refer to the long-term repeatability. It was found that the repeatability is often slightly better, but still similar to the reproducibility. Thus, one can be used to estimate the other.

During the internal validation, six replicates of the same ERM batches were measured in parallel at BAM. The results are correlated in a sense that many usually variable parameters were basically the same (such as air pressure,

performance of the measurement device, temperature in the laboratory etc.). This reduces the variability of the results to only a few remaining parameters, such as the homogeneity of the materials (**Table 5**). Very good homogeneities were found for the toluene impregnated C 45/4 (granulate) and the D-limonene loaded μ -capsule sample. Mediocre homogeneities were found for the n-hexane and 2-ethyl-1-hexanol impregnated C 40/4 (granulate) samples.

Table 5. Results of the in-batch repeatability test. Six replicates of the same ERM batches were measured in parallel. The toluene impregnated C 45/4 (granulate) and the D-limonene loaded μ -capsule sample are highly homogenous. The n-hexane and 2-ethyl-1-hexanol impregnated C 40/4 (granulate) samples revealed only mediocre homogeneities.

	C 40/4 <i>n</i> -hexane	C 45/4 toluene	C 40/4 2-ethyl-1-hexanol	μ -capsules D-limonene
mean <i>ER</i> [$\mu\text{g}/\text{h}\times\text{g}$]	24.0	36.2	28.2	13.1
SD [$\mu\text{g}/\text{h}\times\text{g}$]	3.5	1.1	5.3	0.9
relative SD [%]	14.5	3.0	18.6	6.7

Furthermore, a reproducibility and a short and long-term stability study were conducted with the same materials. Air-tight packages were distributed to Eurofins and BAM and stored for different times and at different temperatures. No trend was found for any of the storage conditions. High and low values were obtained for short and long storage times (0, 0.5, 1, 3, 6 and 12 months), as well as for each temperature (-18, 5, 23 and 35 °C) [8].

Since the storage does not seem to have any influence, we used the same results to calculate the in-batch reproducibility (**Table 6**). The testings were conducted at two different laboratories and over 12 months, so it kind of resembles the top-down approach. This way, the reproducibility reveals the variability of the overall emission test chamber procedure and the ERM. Both partners produced very similar average emission rates and relative standard deviations.

Table 6. Results of the in-batch reproducibility (values taken from the investigation of storage conditions). The results of BAM and Eurofins are very similar. The relative standard deviation can be used as a measure for the variability of the overall emission test chamber procedure.

	C 40/4 <i>n</i> -hexane	C 45/4 toluene	C 40/4 2-ethyl-1-hexanol	μ -capsules D-limonene
mean <i>ER</i> [$\mu\text{g}/\text{h}\times\text{g}$] BAM	21.5	31.2	23.0	9.5
mean <i>ER</i> [$\mu\text{g}/\text{h}\times\text{g}$] Eurofins	22.4	30.4	19.9	13.2
mean <i>ER</i> [$\mu\text{g}/\text{h}\times\text{g}$] both	21.9	30.8	21.4	11.4

standard deviation [$\mu\text{g}/\text{h}\times\text{g}$] BAM	5.1	7.0	6.6	4.3
standard deviation [$\mu\text{g}/\text{h}\times\text{g}$] Eurofins	6.5	7.1	7.0	5.8
standard deviation [$\mu\text{g}/\text{h}\times\text{g}$] both	5.7	6.9	6.7	5.3
rel. SD [%] BAM	23.9	22.3	28.5	44.8
rel. SD [%] Eurofins	28.9	23.2	35.1	44.2
rel. SD [%] both	26.2	22.4	31.4	47.0

The reproducibility values obtained from the internal validation are summarized together with values from the development and the ILC part 2 (**Table 7**). The repeatability/reproducibility is highly dependent on the specific ERM.

Table 7. Values of in-batch and batch-to-batch repeatability/reproducibility of ERMs given as relative standard deviation.

ERM / granules, powders and μ - capsules	In-batch rep. of the ER 14 days after loading [%]			Batch-to-batch rep. of the ER 14 days after loading [%]
	a	b	c	a
C 40/4 [toluene]	17	18		39
C 40/4 [2-ethyl-1- hexanol]		66	31	15
C 45/4 [n-hexane]			26	18
C 45/4 [toluene]			22	28
BEA [n-hexane]		57		9
BEA [toluene]				12
BEA [2-ethyl-1-hexanol]				12
μ -capsules HDTTL [D- limonene]		36	47	

^a Repeatability taken from development. ^b Reproducibility taken from ILC part 2. ^c Repeatability taken from internal validation.

The batch-to-batch repeatability is not very good in general. The best batch-to-batch repeatability was found for BEA impregnated with *n*-hexane, though the in-batch reproducibility of that ERM is worse than that of some other materials. Materials with a very good in-batch repeatability (such as C 40/4 impregnated with toluene) exhibit a rather poor batch-to-batch repeatability. However, the in-batch reproducibility is much more important, because the batch-to-batch reproducibility can be easily circumvented by producing very big batches of ERM. In a study on

long-term stability, it was proven, that the ERMs are quite stable, so that large batches of ERM can be produced, characterised, and used for up to 12 months.

4 Uncertainty of gPRM and gCRM

4.1 Uncertainty of the dynamic gPRM

The VOC mole fractions obtained with the dynamic method used can be calculated according to **Eq. 1**.

$$x_i = x_{i(S)} \frac{\bar{q}_m}{q_{v(n_2+air)}} \frac{q_{v(stage\ 1)}}{q_{v(stage\ 1)} + q_{v(air)}} \frac{V_m}{M_i} 1,000,000 \quad \text{Eq. 1}$$

where:

x_i : Fraction of VOC i in the gas-phase standard (nmol mol^{-1})

$x_{i(S)}$: Mass fraction of VOC i in the solution (g g^{-1})

$q_{v(n_2+air)}$: Flow of nitrogen and air at standard conditions (L min^{-1})

$q_{v(stage\ 1)}$: Flow from stage 1 gas mixture at standard conditions (L min^{-1})

$q_{v(air)}$: Flow of air added to the stage 1 gas mixture at standard conditions (L min^{-1})

V_m : Molar volume ($24.0551 \text{ L mol}^{-1}$) at standard conditions

M_i : Molar mass VOC i (g mol^{-1})

The uncertainty of the fraction was calculated according to the GUM [10] from **Eq. 1 (Table 8)**.

Table 8. Uncertainty budget for $50.5 \text{ nmol mol}^{-1}$ *n*-Hexane in dynamic gPRM. The expanded uncertainty in this case is $2.4 \text{ nmol mol}^{-1}$ ($k = 2$), which is equal to a relative expanded uncertainty of 5 %.

Measurand	Value	Distribution	Standard uncertainty	Sensitivity	Uncertainty contribution
$x_{n\text{-Hexane}(S)}$	0.1250 g g^{-1}	Normal	0.0013 g g^{-1}	$4.04 \cdot 10^2$	$5.05 \cdot 10^{-1} \text{ nmol mol}^{-1}$
\bar{q}_m	$1.33 \cdot 10^6 \text{ ng min}^{-1}$	Normal	$2.67 \cdot 10^4 \text{ ng min}^{-1}$	$3.79 \cdot 10^{-5}$	$1.01 \text{ nmol mol}^{-1}$
$q_{v(n_2+air)}$	$11.804 \text{ L min}^{-1}$	Normal	0.058 L min^{-1}	-4.28 ng	$0.247 \text{ nmol mol}^{-1}$
$q_{v(stage\ 1)}$	$0.1002 \text{ L min}^{-1}$	Normal	0.004 L min^{-1}	$5.04 \cdot 10^2$	$2.04 \cdot 10^{-1} \text{ nmol mol}^{-1}$
$q_{v(stage\ 1)} + q_{v(air)}$	7.828 L min^{-1}	Normal	0.26 L min^{-1}	-6.45	$-1.68 \cdot 10^{-1} \text{ nmol mol}^{-1}$
V_m	$24.055 \text{ L mol}^{-1}$	Rectangular	0.024 L mol^{-1}	2.10	$5.05 \cdot 10^{-2} \text{ nmol mol}^{-1}$
M_i	$86.175 \text{ g mol}^{-1}$	Normal	0.004 g mol^{-1}	$-5.86 \cdot 10^{-1}$	$-2.13 \cdot 10^{-3} \text{ nmol mol}^{-1}$
$m_{n\text{-Hexane}}$	$50.5 \text{ nmol mol}^{-1}$	Normal	$1.2 \text{ nmol mol}^{-1}$		

4.2 Uncertainty static gPRM

Uncertainty sources that need to be considered for the static gPRM are:

- Uncertainty for the preparation of the gPRM and sampling into sorbent tubes for the analysis (u_{prep} , Deliverable D3, **Table 10**). The standard uncertainty of the VOC fractions in the static gas mixtures are calculated according to ISO 6142-1 giving a relative standard uncertainty of 0.015 %. Sampling of the static gas mixture into sorbent tubes gives a relative standard uncertainty of 0.5 % (u_{cal} , **Table 10**).
- Calibration of the measurement method with the dynamic gas mixtures sampled into tubes, see section 4.1, gives a relative standard uncertainty of 2.5 %.
- Measurement uncertainty for the verification (u_{meas} , Deliverable D3, **Table 10**). When using the ME sorbent tubes relative standard uncertainties between 1.1 % and 10 % are assigned based on the VOC.
- Uncertainty contribution for the stability based on the results obtained with the Experis VOC cylinder treatment (u_{stab} , **Table 10**).

As both the dynamic and static gPRMs are analysed by sampling the gas mixtures into sorbent tubes to obtain the gCRM the uncertainty of the gPRM and gCRM are the same, sampling of the sorbent tubes does not increase the uncertainty as the uncertainty contribution is small.

Based on these uncertainty sources the uncertainties of the amount fractions of the components in the static gPRM have been calculated according to the GUM [10] (**Table 9** and **Table 10**). The uncertainty for phenol were not determined, as it was evident from visual inspection of the data that the mixtures were unstable with respect to the amount fraction of this component.

Table 9. Uncertainty of n-hexane in a static gPRM. The relative expanded uncertainty in this case is 13 % ($k = 2$). Four uncertainty sources are taking into account 1) sampling of the sorbent tube from the static gPRM (u_{prep}), uncertainty of the calibration standards (u_{cal}), in this case the dynamic gPRM sampled into sorbent tubes, 3) the measurement uncertainty (u_{meas}), and 4) the uncertainty contribution for the stability (u_{stab}).

Measurand	Value	Distribution	Relative standard uncertainty (%)	Sensitivity
u_{prep}	99.9 ng	Normal	0.5	1
u_{cal}	99.9 ng	Normal	2.5	1
u_{meas}	99.9 ng	Normal	1.2	1
u_{stab}	99.9 ng	Normal	5.7	1
$u_{n-Hexane}$	99.9 ng	Normal	6.3	

Table 10. Relative expanded uncertainty (U) for the mass sampled into ME sorbent tubes for each VOC from a static gas mixture with a Experis VOC cylinder treatment ($k = 2$).

VOC	u_{prep} (%)	u_{cal} (%)	u_{meas} (%)	u_{stab} (%)	u (%)	U (%)
n-hexane	0.5	2.5	1.2	5.7	6.3	13

MIBK	0.5	2.5	1.1	2.8	3.9	8
Toluene	0.5	2.5	1.2	2.8	3.9	8
Butyl acetate	0.5	2.5	1.6	7.7	8.3	16
Cyclohexanone	0.5	2.5	2.5	7.3	8.1	16
o-Xylene	0.5	2.5	1.1	3.0	4.1	8
1,3,5-TMB	0.5	2.5	1.5	4.0	5.0	10

The objective in the MetrIAQ project is to obtain gPRMs with a relative expanded uncertainty smaller than 5 %. When the gPRM is obtained via dynamic methods a relative expanded uncertainty of 5 % is obtained. For the static gPRM the relative expanded uncertainty ranges from 8–16 %, for these gas mixtures the objective has not been reached.

During the MetrIAQ ILC, dynamic gPRMs were used to set the reference value [11]. The ILC showed that the gPRMs were suitable to determine the reference value.

4.3 Uncertainty gCRMs in sorbent tubes

As both the dynamic and static gPRMs are analysed by sampling the gas mixtures into sorbent tubes to obtain the gCRM the uncertainty of the gPRM and gCRM are the same, sampling of the sorbent tubes does not increase the uncertainty as the uncertainty contribution is small. The mass sampled into the sorbent tubes can be calculated according to **Eq. 2** for dynamic gPRM.

$$m_i = x_{i(S)} \frac{\bar{q}_m}{q_{v(n_2+air)}} \frac{q_{v(stage\ 1)}}{q_{v(stage\ 1)} + q_{v(air)}} q_{v(sample)} t \cdot 1,000,000 \quad \text{Eq. 2}$$

where:

m_i : Mass VOC i sampled onto the sorbent tube (ng)

$q_{v(sample)}$: Pumped sampling flow at standard conditions (mL min^{-1})

t : Sampling time (min)

The uncertainty of the mass was calculated according to the GUM [10] from **Eq. 2** (**Table 11**).

Table 11. Uncertainty budget for 127 ng n -hexane sampled into a sorbent tube from the dynamic gPRM (u_{cal}). The expanded uncertainty in this case is 6 ng ($k = 2$), which is equal to a relative expanded uncertainty of 5 %.

Measurand	Value	Distribution	Standard uncertainty	Sensitivity	Uncertainty contribution
$x_{n-Hexane(S)}$	0.1250 g g^{-1}	Normal	0.0013 g g^{-1}	$1.02 \cdot 10^3$	1.27 ng
\bar{q}_m	$1.33 \cdot 10^6 \text{ ng min}^{-1}$	Normal	$2.67 \cdot 10^4 \text{ ng min}^{-1}$	$9.53 \cdot 10^{-5}$	2.54 ng
$q_{v(n_2+air)}$	11.804 L min^{-1}	Normal	0.058 L min^{-1}	$-1.08 \cdot 10^1$	$-6.22 \cdot 10^{-1}$ ng
$q_{v(stage\ 1)}$	0.1002 L min^{-1}	Normal	0.004 L min^{-1}	$1.27 \cdot 10^3$	$5.13 \cdot 10^{-1}$ ng
$q_{v(stage\ 1)} + q_{v(air)}$	7.828 L min^{-1}	Normal	0.26 L min^{-1}	$-1.62 \cdot 10^1$	$-4.22 \cdot 10^{-1}$ ng

$Q_v(\text{sample})$	0.05017 L min ⁻¹	Normal	0.00023 L min ⁻¹	2.53 10 ³	5.90 10 ⁻¹ ng
T	14.000 min	Normal	0.015 min	9.08	1.36 10 ⁻¹ ng
$m_{n\text{-Hexane}}$	127 ng	Normal	3.0 ng		

5 Conclusion

In this report, the uncertainty budgets of ERMs, gPRMs and gCRMs are described. Since ERMs are no primary reference materials, only the measurement uncertainty can be determined. Different aspects, such as the uncertainty of analysis, of the emission test chamber procedure and of the ERMs, are elucidated. Bearing in mind the relatively high uncertainty of the overall procedure, very good in-batch reproducibilities (18 % and 22 % respectively at day 14 after loading) were found for activated carbon C 40/4 and C 45/4 impregnated with toluene. Mixed results were obtained for the batch-to-batch reproducibility, though the in-batch reproducibility seems much more important. Unlike the in-batch reproducibility, the batch-to-batch reproducibility can be circumvented by producing very big batches. The high stability of ERMs enables quite long storage times of up to 12 months, which supports this work-around.

Based on the validation and stability study of the gPRM and gCRM the uncertainty was determined. A relative expanded uncertainty of 5 % was obtained for gPRMs prepared dynamically. Static gPRMs, in cylinders, have relative expanded uncertainties between 8–16 %.

With this, the aims of the deliverable and Objective 3 have been fully achieved.

Annex 1 Validation data of the analysis method used for the emission testing of ERMs

A1.1 Repeatability data

The repeatability was calculated as the standard deviation of five consecutive measurements of the QC standard (**Table 12**).

Table 12. Measurement data used for the calculation of the repeatability (sr). The five measurements were conducted on the same day.

#	Substance [ng]			
	<i>n</i> -hexane	toluene	2-ethyl-1-hexanol	D-limonene
1	100.35	102.37	103.12	101.88
2	93.04	100.06	103.07	100.52
3	103.35	100.05	104.98	103.67
4	104.78	98.95	104.91	99.76
5	101.77	103.57	104.54	103.25
Mean [ng]	100.66	101.00	104.12	101.82
SD [ng]	4.57	1.90	0.95	1.69
RSD [%]	4.54	1.88	0.92	1.66

A1.2 Reproducibility data

The reproducibility was calculated as the standard deviation of eight measurements of the QC standard over the course of four weeks (**Table 13**).

Table 13. Measurement data used for the calculation of the reproducibility (sR). The eight measurements were conducted over the course of four weeks.

#	Substance [ng]			
	<i>n</i> -hexane	toluene	2-ethyl-1-hexanol	D-limonene
1	100.81	100.48	95.40	100.49
2	109.51	103.71	110.14	101.76
3	105.24	101.23	100.16	99.72
4	108.76	104.79	111.47	102.83
5	106.88	98.21	100.20	98.55
6	105.28	98.63	101.85	100.41
7	105.84	96.71	96.04	98.01
8	93.99	100.05	100.93	100.09
Mean [ng]	104.54	100.48	102.02	100.23
SD [ng]	5.02	2.74	5.89	1.57
RSD [%]	4.80	2.73	5.77	1.57

Annex 2 Exemplary chamber characterisation of a chamber used for the emission testing of ERMs

A2.1 Homogeneity and stability of temperature and relative humidity

An array of sensors was distributed within and outside of the chamber (**Figure 2**). The sensors recorded data for temperature and humidity for several hours.

Figure 2. Scheme of the 1 m³ emission test chamber and the distribution of sensors. Five sensors were located at the back of the chamber right in front of the ventilator, five sensors were in the front of the chamber right behind the door, the reference sensor (highly accurate) was in the middle of the chamber, and one sensor was outside of the chamber.

A2.2 Pressure

A pressure sensor was placed into the 1 m³ chamber for about four days. The recorded pressure was then compared to the measured pressure of the nearby weather station Berlin-Dahlem (**Figure 3**). The difference between the two curves is about 1 hPa. This proves that the pressure determined by the weather station can be used, when corrected by +1 hPa. The pressure and its fluctuation are however highly dependent on the weather.

Figure 3. Comparison of the pressure measured within the chamber and by the weather station Berlin-Dahlem.

A2.3 Air exchange rate

The air exchange rate was determined with help of the tracer gas method [12]. In brief, a small proportion of N_2O (500–1000 ppm) is dosed into the chamber air. Then the decay of the concentration is tracked over time with help on a FT-IR device. The formula of the resulting curve is determined (**Eq. 3**), and the air exchange rate is extracted from the decaying factor (**Eq. 4**).

$$c(t) = c_0 * e^{-n*t} \quad \text{Eq. 3}$$

$$n = \frac{\ln \frac{C_1}{C_2}}{\Delta t} \quad \text{Eq. 4}$$

The air exchange rate for different inlet flow settings of the chamber is depicted (**Figure 4**). The relation of the air exchange rate and the air inlet flow is linear. The chamber was set to 25 %, which equals to 0.509 h^{-1} according to the linear regression equation. The value was verified in an additional experiment (not shown here).

Figure 4. Air exchange rates determined with the tracer gas method.

A2.4 Air flow velocity over sample

A hot-wire anemometer (ALNOR GGA-26 ANE-126) was placed at different positions in the chamber (**Figure 5**). Position 5 marks the absolute middle of the chamber ($[0, 0, 0]$ on an imaginary cartesian coordination system with $[x, y, z]$ being $[\text{width}, \text{height}, \text{depth}]$). Position 9 is still in the origin of the x- and y-axis, but 20 cm closer to the ventilator ($[0, 0, -20]$). Position 1 is 20 cm closer to the door ($[0, 0, 20]$). Positions 10–12 are below Position 9, each point is 10 cm lower than the point before ($[0, -(10-30), -20]$). Positions 6–8 are below position 5 but lower ($[0, -(10-30), 0]$), and positions 2–4 are below position 1 but lower ($[0, -(10-30), 20]$).

Figure 5. A hot-wire anemometer (ALNOR GGA-26 ANE-126) was placed at different position within the chamber to determine the air flow velocity.

The air velocities and their standard deviations found for the different positions are depicted in **Figure 6**. Position 7 was used for the experiments, because it has a mean value of 0.2 m/s and a fluctuation of 0.1 m/s. This means, the air velocity at this position is within the required velocity of 0.1–0.3 m/s for most of the time.

Figure 6. Air flow velocity and its standard deviation at the different positions.

Annex 3 Results stability study static gPRMs

Figure 7. Graphic presentation of the stability results for the VOCs in static gPRM VSL114005. First point in the graph is the gravimetric amount fraction. The other points are the calculated amount fractions based on the measurements. The dotted lines indicate the expanded uncertainty determined for the VOC in the static gPRM.

Figure 8. Graphic presentation of the stability results for the VOCs in static gPRM VSL114043. First point in the graph is the gravimetric amount fraction. The other points are the calculated amount fractions based on the measurements. The dotted lines indicate the expanded uncertainty determined for the VOC in the static gPRM.

Figure 9. Graphic presentation of the stability results for the VOCs in static gPRM VSL114044. First point in the graph is the gravimetric amount fraction. The other points are the calculated amount fractions based on the measurements. The dotted lines indicate the expanded uncertainty determined for the VOC in the static gPRM.

Figure 10. Graphic presentation of the stability results for the VOCs in static gPRM VSL114045. First point in the graph is the gravimetric amount fraction. The other points are the calculated amount fractions based on the measurements. The dotted lines indicate the expanded uncertainty determined for the VOC in the static gPRM.

Figure 11. Graphic presentation of the stability results for the VOCs in static gPRM VSL187546. First point in the graph is the gravimetric amount fraction. The other points are the calculated amount fractions based on the measurements. The dotted lines indicate the expanded uncertainty determined for the VOC in the static gPRM.

Figure 12. Graphic presentation of the stability results for the VOCs in static gPRM VSL187555. First point in the graph is the gravimetric amount fraction. The other points are the calculated amount fractions based on the measurements. The dotted lines indicate the expanded uncertainty determined for the VOC in the static gPRM.

Figure 13. Graphic presentation of the stability results for the VOCs in static gPRM VSL270608. First point in the graph is the gravimetric amount fraction. The other points are the calculated amount fractions based on the measurements. The dotted lines indicate the expanded uncertainty determined for the VOC in the static gPRM.

Figure 14. Graphic presentation of the stability results for the VOCs in static gPRM VSL361130. First point in the graph is the gravimetric amount fraction. The other points are the calculated amount fractions based on the measurements. The dotted lines indicate the expanded uncertainty determined for the VOC in the static gPRM.

References

1. EN 16516, *Construction products - Assessment of release of dangerous substances - Determination of emissions into indoor air (EN 16516:2017+A1:2020)*. 2020, European Committee for Standardization (CEN): DIN Media, Berlin.
2. van der Veen, A.M.H., et al., *Uncertainty calculations in the certification of reference materials 4. Characterisation and certification*. Accreditation and Quality Assurance, 2001. **6**(7): p. 290-294.
3. Linsinger, T.P.J., et al., *Homogeneity and stability of reference materials*. Accreditation and Quality Assurance, 2001. **6**(1): p. 20-25.
4. ISO 6142-1, *Gas Analysis - Preparation of calibration gas mixtures - Part 1: Gravimetric method for Class I mixtures (ISO 6142-1:2015)*. 2015, International Organization for Standardization (ISO): DIN Media, Berlin.
5. ISO 6145-4, *Gas Analysis - Preparation of calibration gas mixtures using dynamic volumetric methods - Part 4: Continuous syringe injection method (ISO 6145-4:2004)*. 2004, International Organization for Standardization: DIN Media, Berlin.
6. ISO 16017-1, *Indoor, ambient and workplace air - Sampling and analysis of volatile organic compounds by sorbent tube/thermal desorption/capillary gas chromatography - Part 1: Pumped sampling (ISO 16017-1:2000)*. 2000, International Organization for Standardization (ISO): DIN Media, Berlin.
7. Musyanovych, A., et al., *Report on the development and performance of the prototype emission reference material (ERM), demonstrating an emission profile that decreases by less than 10 % over at least 14 days, including information about the reservoir materials, source strength, mass transport modelling, and the results of emissions tests - Deliverable D1 of the EMPIR project 20NRM04 MetrIAQ*. 2024.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12545171>
8. Grimmer, C., T. Neuhaus, and A. Musyanovych, *Guideline for the use of the ERM for the improvement of the QA/QC of the emission chamber test method in EN 16516, including a description of (i) the optimal storage conditions, (ii) loading into the emission test chambers and (iii) a sampling and measurement protocol - Deliverable D2 of the EMPIR project 20NRM04 MetrIAQ*. 2024. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12544117>
9. de Krom, I., et al., *Report on the preparation and analysis of gPRMs and gCRMs of indoor air pollutants stated in the EU-LCI list with relative uncertainties below 5 % ($k = 2$) and a shelf life of at least 1 year - Deliverable D3 of the EMPIR project 20NRM04 MetrIAQ*. 2024.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10656469>

10. BIPM, *Evaluation of measurement data – Guide to the expression of uncertainty in measurement (JCGM 100:2008)*. 2008, Joint Committee for Guides in Metrology.
11. de Krom, I., et al., *Summary report on the evaluation of the inter-laboratory comparison performed with the ERM and gCRMs: including information on the repeatability and reproducibility of the data and an evaluation of the major uncertainty sources in sampling, analysis and reporting, according to the EN 16516 test method - Deliverable D5 of the EMPIR project 20NRM04 MetrIAQ*. 2024. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12545048>
12. VDI 4300-7, *Indoor air pollution measurement - Measurement of indoor air change rate (VDI 4300-7:2001)*. 2001, Beuth: Berlin. p. 7.